

Elevator Pitch Exercise

Elevator Pitch Instructions:

- Read definition of an elevator pitch, below
- Using the guiding documentation and prompt on page 2, create your own elevator pitch as a draft for your scholarly communication or advocacy role, or for a particular event that you can foresee attending in the future. Use the “Guide” and “Prompt,” below.
- Optionally, share your draft of the elevator pitch with the course instructors and class participants on the W23 slack channel. If you’d like feedback, then please ask!
- Keep a copy of your work for future use.
- Download the exercise files if you are interested in writing other drafts of your own customized elevator pitches in the future.

Note: if you use this exercise, or the original, please attribute and credit, and let us know. Please note the below credit and attribution section.

Elevator Pitch Definition:

- What is an elevator pitch?
- Around 30 seconds long (short enough to deliver in an elevator ride)
- Could be 1-4 sentences, or 1-3 minutes if a longer pitch is necessary (a longer but still brief time span, such as a walk to a meeting or waiting for a digital event to start)
- Should spark interest and may or may not elicit a response, depending on situation
- Conversation starter, a way to introduce yourself, or network
- Is clear and authoritative
- Highlights your value and what problem you are solving, or provides an entry to a topic
- Introduces your uniqueness in the moment
- Uses language that is everyday, understandable, approachable

Elevator Pitch Examples

Thank you for asking about the Libraries’ support for Article Processing Charges (APCs) to make your journal article open access! We don’t currently provide this support.

However, may I recommend you consider depositing your work to UAlbany’s institutional repository? Not only will you preserve your scholarship, but you will enjoy increased discoverability and impact metrics.

Our repository manager will help you review your licensing terms and upload the appropriate file to Scholars Archive.

Elevator Pitch Exercise: Session One Optional Exercise

OR I'm the Scholarly Communications librarian here, and that means I work supporting research, scholarship, and grants across the university. With our university invested in making an impact on global citizen engagement, the services my unit provides are wide ranging and support faculty, students, staff, and the public. Would you be interested in a meeting over coffee or tea in the coming month, according to your teaching schedule?

Prompt and Guide: Elevator pitch exercise - create your own

I am a _____

your role

who works with

your collaborators

to _____,

what you do / value proposition

so that _____

the greater benefit

_____.

My goal is to

_____.

why you / your work matters

Elevator Pitch Exercise: Session One Optional Exercise

Credit and Attribution:

This optional exercise relating to Session 1 is adapted from is another work. Attribution, with thanks, goes to Amin, K., & Taylor, A. S. (2020). Elevator Pitch Exercise Template and Examples. *UCSF: Library*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/1343b9dq>

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